

IMPACT OF BEING JOB PERFECT TOWARDS CAPACITY BUILDING AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract

This research paper evaluates the impact of a capacity building initiative titled 'Being Job Perfect' organized by Pillai College of Education and Research (PCER) for final semester B.Ed students. The sessions focused on three core areas—resume writing, mock interviews, and expert talks—aimed at preparing teacher trainees for professional life. A structured Google Form survey was administered to 40 participants from the B.Ed programme. Based on responses to 20 Likert-scale statements, a heatmap was generated by condensing each statement into a single keyword and visually representing the level of agreement using a defined colour code. The findings suggest that students benefited significantly, particularly from the resume writing and mock interview sessions. This paper discusses the effectiveness of each session, interpretations from the heatmap, and gives recommendations for future improvements.

1. Introduction

In today's rapidly transforming educational environment, it is increasingly important for teacher education programs to focus not only on pedagogical knowledge and classroom management skills but also on preparing student teachers to confidently enter the professional world. With a growing emphasis on career readiness and employability, institutions must address the practical challenges student teachers face as they transition from college to the workforce. Recognizing the vital need for building the capacities of student teachers to equip them with the knowledge and skills beyond the curricular transactions, Pillai College of Education and Research (PCER), Chembur, introduced an initiative titled 'Being Job Perfect' for the final-semester B. Ed students. This program was specifically designed to bridge the gap between academic preparation and job expectations.

The objectives of this program were as follows:

- To train student teachers in writing effective and professional resumes.

- To build confidence and enhance performance during job interviews through structured preparation.
- To expose students to expert guidance and real-world experiences through insightful professional talks.

The aim of this program was to reduce job-related anxiety, boost self-confidence, and facilitate a smooth transition from academic life to the teaching profession. To assess the effectiveness of this program, student feedback was collected and systematically analyzed.

2. Sample

The study sample comprised 41 second-year B.Ed students from PCER, who were in their fourth and final semester. These students had attended most or all sessions under the “Being Job Perfect” program. A purposive sampling method was employed to ensure that the responses accurately reflected the experiences with these sessions.

3. Methodology

A quantitative survey design was used to assess student perceptions. Feedback was gathered through a structured Google Form containing 20 statements. Each statement was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with:

1 = Strongly Agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Disagree and 5 = Strongly Disagree

These statements were grouped into three areas:

- Resume Writing
- Mock Interviews
- Expert Talks

After collecting the responses, the data was statistically analyzed, and a heatmap was developed to visually present the trends.

4. Tool Used

The primary tool for data collection was the Job Perfect Feedback Form, administered via Google Form. The tool consisted of 20 Likert-scale statements, each aligned with one of the three key areas of the program: resume writing, mock interviews, and expert talks.

Data Analysis

After collecting the feedback, the data was analyzed. Each of the 20 statements included in the Google Form was rated by the students on a 5-point Likert scale. To simplify the analysis and enhance the visual clarity of the data, each statement was condensed into a single keyword (e.g., *Resume Tips*, *Confidence*, *Insight*). The average scores for each keyword were then color-coded and represented in a heatmap. The heatmap followed a color scheme, with each color

corresponding to a specific rating range: Red (1) represented “Strongly Agree,” Yellow (2) indicated “Agree,” Light Green (3) signified “Neutral,” Green (4) reflected “Disagree,” and Dark Green (5) indicated “Strongly Disagree.” This color-coded visualization enabled easy identification of areas where the program was most effective and areas where improvements could be considered.

Fig: Heat map representing the scores

The heatmap showed which areas of the program were more beneficial for the student teachers and which ones could be improved. The dominance of red and yellow colours in the heatmap showed that most students gave positive feedback.

Interpretation of Data

The feedback collected from students gave useful insights into how effective each part of the “Being Job Perfect” program was.

For the resume writing sessions, most students strongly agreed that these sessions helped them present their achievements clearly and professionally. Many also said they received helpful advice on how to show their teaching experience in the best way. The average ratings for these statements were between 1.5 and 2.2, which means most students were very happy with these sessions. Overall, students felt more confident about writing their resumes after attending the sessions.

The mock interview sessions also got very positive responses. The average rating was around 1.8, showing strong agreement. Students said these mock interviews helped them deal with nervousness and improved how they communicate during real interviews. Practising with questions and getting feedback gave them a chance to learn and improve in a comfortable and supportive setting.

The expert talks had more mixed responses. While many students agreed that these talks gave them useful information, some were neutral. The average scores for this part ranged between

2.7 and 3.0, which means there is scope for improvement. This shows that how interesting and useful an expert talk is may depend on the speaker's style and the topic discussed.

Looking at all 20 feedback statements together, the average scores were between 1.6 and 2.3, showing that overall, students were happy with the program. Most students said the sessions helped them feel more ready for job interviews and professional life.

Research Findings

The findings of the study show that the "Being Job Perfect" program helped prepare final-semester B.Ed students for a job of a teacher.

In the resume writing section, more than 90% of the students said that the sessions helped them a lot. They learned how to make their resumes better by personalizing them, organizing their content, and highlighting their strengths to match what employers in schools are looking for.

The mock interviews turned out to be the most successful part of the program. Students said the practice interviews felt very real and gave them a chance to answer questions confidently. These sessions helped them reduce nervousness, stay calm, and improve their body language and communication.

Feedback about the expert talks was mixed. Many students found the talks useful and informative, but some gave average ratings. This shows that for these sessions to be more effective, the speakers should be interesting, knowledgeable, and talk about topics that relate directly to teaching. Students also said they would prefer talks that are more interactive and practical.

Overall, the students appreciated the "Being Job Perfect" program. They felt it not only prepared them for interviews but also gave them the confidence and skills needed for professional life. The program was seen as a valuable addition to their teacher training and helped them feel more ready to start their teaching career.

Conclusion

The "Being Job Perfect" program at PCER has been very helpful in preparing B.Ed students for their careers. The program focused on practical skills like resume writing, speaking confidently, and performing well in interviews. The positive feedback from students, supported by the survey results and the heatmap, shows that the program was successful. The high ratings for resume and mock interview sessions highlight the importance of hands-on learning, especially in reducing anxiety and boosting confidence. However, the expert talks showed areas that can be improved for better engagement. Overall, this program proves the importance of

including job readiness training in teacher education, ensuring students are not only skilled teachers but also well-prepared for the teaching job.

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